

EQL0D Burnup Tool and GEMS/HERACLES Coupling for Fluoride MSR Off-gas Reprocessing Stream Modeling

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ABSTRACT

MSRs rely on various online reprocessing techniques to allow continuous, uninterrupted operation. Normally, fertile material is introduced for breeding purposes and Fission Products (FPs) are removed employing different salt reprocessing techniques. To simulate these effects in burnup codes, pseudo-decay constants are employed. The specific cycle time depends on the reprocessing scheme employed to remove each nuclide. In the current implementation of the PSI EQL0D point-burnup code, fuel reprocessing is modeled by effectively multiplying the nuclide concentrations by these constants, representing their extraction from the system. However, for volatility-based reprocessing schemes such as the off-gas system, this method assumes that all chemical species formed from the removed element exist in the gaseous phase. To address this limitation, a Gibbs Energy Minimizer Software (GEMS) employing the HERACLES Thermodynamic DataBase (TDB) developed at PSI has been coupled to the EQL0D procedure. This coupling enables a more accurate representation of gaseous compound speciation and extraction within the off-gas system. To achieve this objective, the reprocessing matrix is adjusted by weighting each extracted element according to its corresponding phase fraction, ensuring a more physically consistent treatment of FP removal.

Keywords: MSR, off-gas, speciation, coupling, pseudo-decay constant

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are one of the six Generation-IV reactor concepts [1]. Compared to the other five designs, MSRs employ molten salts as a coolant, with most designs also employing the molten salt as a fuel carrier. The latter entail advantages over more conventional solid-fueled systems such as more negative feedback coefficients due to the larger thermal expansion of the salt, high fuel burnup resulting in higher resource utilization and the possibility of continuous actinide refilling and online Fission Product (FP) removal [2].

Online FP removal from the fuel is a unique characteristic of MSRs compared to other conventional systems. Most FPs exhibit large absorption cross sections that hinder the neutronic performance of the system. In traditional systems, refueling outages are required to substitute the most burned fuel elements with fresh ones – replacing the fissioned actinide mass and reducing the amount of FPs in the core– while, in MSRs, the removal of FPs allows reactors to operate uninterrupted for long periods of time with clear economical advantages. In addition, online FP removal allows for less reactivity control systems and opens the door to $^{232}\text{Th} - ^{233}\text{U}$ cycles.

To achieve a correct and efficient removal of FPs from the fuel, a good understanding of the chemistry of the salt – especially on the formation of compounds and their solubility in the salt– is essential to

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choose suitable reprocessing schemes. The Molten Salt Reactor Program (MSRP) at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), aimed at proving the MSR technology for civilian application [3], included the investigation of different reprocessing schemes for fluoride fuel salts.

Among the different FPs, noble gases — krypton and xenon — are of particular concern, as they display large neutron capture cross sections that are detrimental to the neutron economy. During the MSRP, significant effort was invested in the development of an effective technique for noble gas removal, leading to the implementation of the off-gas system.

In the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE), the off-gas system was employed to sparge gaseous FPs out of the primary fuel loop. The off-gas system worked by introducing helium bubbles through the fuel pump bowl which would then transport FPs to activated charcoal absorber beds. The radioactive xenon would be retained on the charcoal for a minimum of 90 days and the krypton for 7 days [4].

For each of the FPs, experiments were performed to determine the cycle times (T_{cycle}) in order to quantify the rates at which these are removed. The cycle time is defined as the time needed to remove the whole inventory of a certain FP from the primary fuel loop. There is extensive literature from the MSRE and the Molten Salt Breeder Reactor (MSBR) on reported cycle times for the removal of different species [5] [6]; Table I illustrates some of the reported cycle times by ORNL during the MSRP with their corresponding reprocessing scheme for the MSBR.

Table I. Reported cycle times for FP removal from the MSBR salt [5].

Elements	Cycle time for salt processing	Mechanism of salt removal
Zn, Ga, Ge, As, Se, Zr, Cd, In, Sn, Sb	200 days	Reductive extraction into bismuth, hydrofluorination into waste LiF-Zr ₄ salt
Br, I	60 days	Volatilization as fluorides in primary fluorination
Kr, Xe	50 sec	Sparged from salt with inert gas in the primary fuel loop
Nb, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Pd, Ag, Te	50 sec	Reduced by metal surfaces in reactor and plated out
La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Pm, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Y	50 days	Reductive extraction into bismuth, concentration in fuel salt for waste discard

The measured cycle times in the MSRP have been extensively used to simulate the removal of FPs in burnup calculations of liquid-fueled MSRs. To this end, a nuclide-specific pseudo-decay constant (λ_{rem}) is introduced.

$$\lambda_{rem} = \frac{1}{T_{cycle}} \quad (1)$$

In much of the available literature, burnup calculations take into account the removal of FPs by introducing the pseudo-decay constants directly through the experimental and simulated cycle times found mainly in the ORNL reports [7] [8]. This method assumes that all FPs designated for extraction in the simulation are present in the target phase and no unintended compounds, such as volatile uranium species $-UF_6$ or UF_4- , are co-extracted.

In 1994, off-gas samples indicated the presence of a considerable volume of UF_6 , revealing a new unexpected pathway for volatilization of MSRE constituents. Around 2.6 kg of uranium were found to be immobilized in the charcoal beds [9]. The presence of fissile material outside of the core poses issues

such as nuclear re-criticality or the potential for the discharge of airborne alpha radionuclides. This highlights the importance of accurately accounting for actinide extraction in the off-gas system.

The aim of this paper is to integrate compound formation and speciation chemistry into MSR burnup calculations in order to assess its impact on the composition of the off-gas reprocessing stream and on the system's neutronic behavior. This is done by coupling the EQL0D point-burnup code with a Gibbs Energy Minimizer Software (GEMS), solved through the HERACLES Thermodynamic DataBase (TDB) developed in PSI.

2. METHODS

2.1. The EQL0D Procedure

The EQL0D procedure is a point-burnup code that was developed in the Advanced Nuclear System group at PSI to handle two types of burnup calculations: fuel evolution over a finite number of steps or searching directly for equilibrium [8]. It is written in MATLAB environment and coupled to Serpent 2 Monte Carlo neutron transport code [10] to obtain reaction rates used by EQL0D for burnup calculations.

For burnup calculations, EQL0D uses the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) [11] to solve the Bateman equations and compute the evolution of the nuclide concentrations through the burnup steps. The general evolution of the concentration of a given nuclide N_i as a function of time can be expressed as

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = -\overline{\sigma_{a,i}}\overline{\phi} N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_i \overline{\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}}\overline{\phi} N_j - \lambda_i N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j N_j \quad (2)$$

for which $\overline{\sigma_{a,i}}\overline{\phi}$ is the total absorption rate by nuclide i , $\gamma_{j \rightarrow i}$ the yield of all decay reactions of nuclide j that result in the production of nuclide i and λ_i the decay constant of nuclide i .

This equation can be extended for liquid-fuel MSR by introducing the term accounting for the nuclide removal due to the off-gas system and the actinide feed term as

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \underbrace{-\overline{\sigma_{a,i}}\overline{\phi} N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_i \overline{\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}}\overline{\phi} N_j}_{\text{flux-induced reactions}} - \underbrace{\lambda_i N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j N_j}_{\text{decay}} - \underbrace{\lambda_{i,rem} N_i}_{\text{off-gas}} + \underbrace{S_i}_{\text{Feed}} \quad (3)$$

where the terms can be divided into flux-dependent, decay and off-gas contributions. The previous equation can be written in matrix form as a summation of a flux-induced reaction matrix \mathbf{B} , a decay matrix \mathbf{D} , a removal or reprocessing matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ and an addition matrix \mathbf{A} .

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{\Lambda} + \mathbf{A} \quad (4)$$

2.2. GEMS/HERACLES Database

The HERACLES-TDB is a thermodynamic database developed at PSI to support the modeling of Uranium, transuranics (TRU) and FPs as well as solid and gaseous speciation [12]. The HERACLES thermodynamic database has been previously coupled with a severe accident code, MELCOR, to improve its FP modeling capabilities and validated through the VERDON facility [13].

In this work, the HERACLES database is coupled with GEMS, developed at PSI [14], to simulate the compound formation and speciation in the fluoride salts.

Due to the corrosive nature of molten salts, a redox control of the salt is to be employed in the simulations using GEMS. Although there are many ways of monitoring it, it was demonstrated in the MSRE at ORNL that redox control can be achieved through the control of UF_4/UF_3 ratio [15]. In the present work, the UF_4/UF_3 ratio is maintained at 70 by controlling the fluorine content in the salt, which lies within the acceptable range of 50–143 [16]. Higher ratios – too reducing conditions– favor the formation of uranium carbides with materials such as graphite moderators and lower ratios – too oxidizing conditions– favor the formation of corrosion products [16].

2.3. EQL0D/GEMS Coupling Scheme

The coupling scheme developed in the present work is portrayed in Figure 1. The EQL0D procedure performs the burnup in the inner loop while the necessary reaction rates given by Serpent are obtained in the outer loop. GEMS is then coupled before the preparation of the initial matrix and inside each of the burnup steps to account for the change in fuel composition. The material composition vector of the fuel is fed into GEMS, which, in turn, returns a list with all formed compounds and their phase.

Two distinct kinds of FPs are modeled, those being Gaseous Fission Products (GFPs) and Solid Fission Products (SFPs). Both are extracted by the off-gas system. For these reasons, both solid and gaseous phase fractions for each element need to be accounted for. To introduce the effects of the compound speciation into the reprocessing matrix, the phase fraction of each element (μ_e^p) is obtained as

$$\mu_e^p = \frac{\sum_c^p n_e^c}{\sum_c n_e^c} \quad (5)$$

where n_e^c denotes the moles of compound c formed by element e . The numerator includes all compounds containing element e in phase p (C_e^p), while the denominator includes all formed compounds containing element e (C_e), irrespective of their phase. The reprocessing matrix is then modified such that each pseudo-decay constant of each nuclide is weighted by the gaseous or solid fraction of the corresponding element. If an element presents no compound in the gaseous or solid phase, the phase fraction is zero and no extraction of the element is performed. Equation (3) can be re-written as

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = -\overline{\sigma_{a,i}\phi} N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_i \overline{\sigma_{j \rightarrow i}\phi} N_j - \lambda_i N_i + \sum_{j \neq i} \gamma_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j N_j - \mu_i^p \lambda_{i,rem} N_i, \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_i^p = \mu_e^p \quad \forall i \in e$$

3. RESULTS

To evaluate the effects of coupling EQL0D with GEMS, three cases were simulated and modeled. One employs the developed EQL0D/GEMS coupling scheme while a second one employs EQL0D standalone. The third case is used to see the effect of introducing into the GFPs stream volatile actinide compounds. In addition, a small sensitivity study to the effects of the redox control on k_{inf} was conducted.

3.1. Simulation setup

For the study cases, the geometry consists of a homogeneous 1 m^3 composed of a $LiF-UF_4-ThF_4$ salt mixture ($T_{salt} = 973.15K$) with a 22.5 mol.% actinide share and reflective boundary conditions. The

Figure 1. Flowchart of the modified EQL0D procedure with GEMS/HERACLES coupling.

initial ratio of Th to U is selected so that the absorption-to-fission ratio is initially unity and the salt is burned for 6.2 years maintaining ^{232}Th mass constant. The nuclear data library ENDF/B-VIII is employed. Similar conditions were employed in the numerical benchmark of SAMOSAFER [17].

Three different cycle times are employed in the off-gas system depending on the phase of the chemical species. A cycle time of 30s is applied to GFPs while SFPs are extracted with a cycle time of 4200s, that is, 140 times larger, as demonstrated in CFD bubbling simulations [18]. Zirconium is extracted with a cycle time of 10500s due to its lower transfer coefficient. When compared with the reprocessing scheme presented in Table I, only three cycle-times are used in the simulated case.

3.2. Off-gas reprocessing stream composition

The speciation and main compound formation for each element computed by GEMS after the simulation is portrayed in Figure 2. It can be seen that the main compound formed by each element is soluble in the salt, specially alkali, alkaline earth metals, lanthanides and actinides. Most transition metals that are considered by GEMS remain insoluble and precipitate in the salt. Noble gases are insoluble and almost completely remain in gaseous form.

H2	No data																Gas	Solid	Salt	Liquid	He
LiF	BeF2													B	C(IV)	N2	O(-II)	F(-I)	Ne		
NaF	MgF2													AlF3	SiF4	P	S	Cl(-I)	Ar		
KF	CaF2	Sc	Ti	V	CrF2	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As4	Se2	LiBr	Kr				
RbF	SrF2	YF3	ZrF4	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I(-I)	Xe				
CsI	BaF2	LaF3	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At	Rn				
FrF	RaF4	AcF3																			
			CeF3	PrF3	NdF3	PmF3	SmF3	EuF3	GdF3	TbF3	DyF3	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu					
			ThF4	PaF4	UF4	NpF3	PuF3	AmF3	Cm	Bk	Cf	Es	Fm	Md	No	Lr					

Figure 2. Main compound speciation of the fuel salt after 6.2 years.

3.3. Multiplication factor

The coupling has a considerable effect on the neutronics. The trivial effect seen in this regard is the evolution of the infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf}) in Figure 3a. It can be observed that, at the end of the simulation, the GEMS/EQL0D coupling simulation yields 1060 pcm less than standalone EQL0D, that is, a 1.14% reduction. The main reason for the discrepancy is the overprediction of the extraction rates of the off-gas system of many of the FPs when multiplying by a uniform pseudo-decay constant. This induces a difference in the absorption reaction rates between both cases. The overprediction on the extraction of the FPs in the off-gas can be clearly seen in Figure 3b.

The high solubility of the actinides demonstrates that the extraction of volatile uranium or thorium compounds is small and has a negligible effect on the neutronics. However, Figure 3b shows that when incorporating the coupling, 0.008 grams of actinides, of which 92% is uranium are extracted through the off-gas system.

The overall percentage change in total absorption reaction rates from coupled to the standalone simulation is approximately -1.12% , indicating that the difference in k_{inf} arises primarily from this effect. In contrast, the total fission reaction rates yield similar values (less than 0.01%) due to power normalization, having no significant impact on the evolution of k_{inf} .

Figure 3. k_{inf} and off-gas stream composition evolution for the simulated cases.

In this work, a study on the sensitivity of the UF_4/UF_3 ratio on k_{inf} was performed. Through simulations of different ratios, it was observed that inside the acceptable range of redox potential, k_{inf} did not experience significant change, with only around 35 pcm difference between the largest and smaller ratio computed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, this work demonstrates the feasibility and importance of coupling GEMS with EQL0D and investigates the implications of accounting for the molten salt chemistry in the off-gas system.

Firstly, a considerable effect on the system's neutronics was observed. This is seen in the evolution of k_{inf} . This is explained by the effects of GEMS speciation in the FP extraction and therefore in their (n, γ) reaction rates. However, it should be noted that the effect that GEMS has on k_{inf} could be overpredicted due to missing elements in the database (Figure 2) that are not extracted when the coupling is done.

Secondly, the speciation and compound formation computed by GEMS, although hard to validate due to lack of experimental results, confirms the presence of elements reported in the MSRE. The presence of HF or Ar, salt residues and noble metals such as Rh and decay products such as Cs, Ba or Rb in the simulated off-gas stream composition show similar behavior to some of the available literature [19]. However, for insoluble volatile elements – particularly noble gases or other species with gas fractions close to unity– the use of a non-weighted pseudo-decay constant provides a reasonable approximation.

Finally, accounting for the speciation of partially soluble FPs can affect the off-gas stream composition, especially regarding total FP and actinide extraction. The modeling of actinide extraction of the off-gas follows behaviors already seen in the MSRE experiment [9].

The present work evaluates only the coupling between chemistry and burnup in fluoride fuel salts. Future works should develop thermodynamic databases for chloride fuel salts to assess similar effects in salts that have less experimental results and expand current fluoride databases. It would be of interest to examine the effect of the salt redox potential on the off-gas stream composition, as different redox conditions may favor the formation of volatile actinide compounds.

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